

Biologically Active Thiazolidinone

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Some new thiazolidinone derivatives with an aromatic nitrogen heterocyclic nucleus as possible amoebicidal, cysticidal and fungicidal agents have been synthesized. They have been also screened for anticonvulsant activity.

THIAZOLIDINONE derivatives are reported to have a wide variety of 'CNS' depressant properties including anaesthetic¹, anticonvulsant² and sedative action³. Antimicrobial activity has been found to be associated with thiazolidinones. They have been investigated as potential amoebicides and fungicides^{4,5}.

2-Aminopyridine was condensed with the arylisothiocyanate to give N-aryl-N'-(2'-Pyridyl)thiocarbamide (I) in 65-80% yield⁶⁻⁷, the latter on being refluxed in glacial acetic acid with chloroacetic acid and fused sodium acetate afforded the corresponding 2-arylimino-3-(2'-pyridyl) thiazolidin-4-one(II). The melting points of the compounds (I) and (II) together with the amoebicidal activities of the latter are reported in Table 1.

TABLE-1. MELTING POINTS (UNCORRECTED) OF COMPOUNDS (I) AND (II) AND THE AMOEBICIDAL ACTIVITIES OF COMPOUNDS II

Sl No.	Substituents	Compd I M.P.°C	Compd. II M.P.°C	Amoebicidal activity*
1.	C ₆ H ₅	160	140	+
2.	C ₆ H ₄ CH ₃ (2)	140	180	+
3.	C ₆ H ₄ CH ₃ (3)	162	170	-
4.	C ₆ H ₄ CH ₃ (4)	143	216	-
5.	C ₆ H ₃ (CH ₃) ₂ (2,4)	180	160	±
6.	C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₃ (2)	200	182	-
7.	C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₃ (4)	145	170	-
8.	C ₆ H ₄ OC ₂ H ₅ (4)	170	190	-
9.	C ₆ H ₄ -Cl(4)	200	215	+
10.	C ₆ H ₄ Br(4)	182	240	±

*(-) Negative culture (+) positive culture
(±) Dead and alive amoebae

Similarly the thiazolidinones (IV) were prepared from 3-amino pyridine via the thiocarbamides (III). Their physical and pharmacological properties are tabulated in Table 2.

TABLE-2. MELTING POINTS (UNCORRECTED) OF COMPOUNDS (III) AND (IV) AND THE AMOEBICIDAL ACTIVITIES OF COMPOUNDS (IV)

Sl No.	Substituents	X	Compd(III) M.P.°C	Compd(IV) M.P.°C	Amoebicidal activity*
1	C ₆ H ₅	H	170	176	+
2	C ₆ H ₄ CH ₃ (4)	H	190	100	-
3	C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₃ (2)	H	180	140	±
4	C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₃ (4)	H	185	105	-
5	C ₆ H ₄ Cl(4)	H	195	140	-
6	C ₆ H ₅	Cl	240	210	+
7	C ₆ H ₄ CH ₃ (4)	Cl	260	185	+
8	C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₃ (2)	Cl	260	220	+
9	C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₃ (4)	Cl	200	190	±
10	C ₆ H ₄ Cl(4)	Cl	180	100	+

*(-) Negative culture (+) positive culture (±) dead and alive amoeba

Pharmacological screening

Determination of amoebicidal activity against *Schizopyrenus russelli* in^a *in vitro*: The amoebae of *S. russelli* were grown in mono bacterial cultures of non-nutrient agar plates (2.5% w/v agar; 0.5% w/v NaCl, pH 6.8-7.0) supplied with a young culture of *Escherichia coli* (2-3 days old grown on nutrient agar slages as food). A dash of fresh *E. coli* was added to freshly harvested amoebae (in 5% saline) to keep the amoebae motile and stretched. One drop of this suspension was taken in each cavity of the cavity slide, and to it double the amount of drug concentration (aqueous solution) to be tested (to compensate for the dilution) was added. Slides were incubated in moist chamber at 25 ± 1° for 24 hrs. After 24 hrs the amoebae were once again observed for judging their viability. (Table 1 and 2).

Determination of cysticidal activity against *schizopyrenus russelli*^a in *in vitro*: Cysts from pure line cultures of *S. russelli* were used in this study. The amoebae were grown in monobacterial cultures on non-nutrient agar plates supplied with a young culture of *E. coli* (2-3 days old) grown on non-nutrient

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agar slants as food. After 5-7 days, cysts were harvested and viable sterile cysts free from bacteria were obtained. Required dilutions of compounds were prepared for determination of their percentage cysticidal and excystment properties. (Table 3)

TABLE—3 EFFECT OF COMPOUNDS(II) ON EXCYSTMENT OF CYSTS OF *S. russelli*

Sl No.	Drug dilution	No. of cysts	No. of cysts excysted	% excystment
3	2 mg/ml	94	-	-
	1 mg/ml	98	-	-
4	2 mg/ml	66	42	63.9
	1 mg/ml	69	56	81.1
7	2 mg/ml	99	-	-
	1 mg/ml	81	49	60.5
10	2 mg/ml	98	-	-
	1 mg/ml	99	-	-

Cysticidal activity of Sl. No. 4 of compounds(II) against cysts of *S. russelli*

Drug dilution	No. of cysts	No. of cysts excysted	% excystment	% cysticidal activity
2 mg/ml	66	42	63.9	36.1
1 mg/ml	69	56	81.9	18.1
0.5 mg/ml	65	20	31.0	69.0
0.25 mg/ml	142	-	-	-
0.125 mg/ml	79	-	-	-
0.0625 mg/ml	27	4	15.0	85.0

Anticonvulsant activity⁹-against Metrazol induced seizures was determined by injecting the drug (5% aqueous suspension in gum acacia) in a dose of 100 mg/kg i.p. to groups of 10 mice of either sex. Pen-tylenetetrazol (80 mg/kg) was injected 1 hr after the administration of the drugs. Mice were observed for 60 min for the occurrence of seizures. Animals free of even threshold convulsion were considered protected (Table 4).

TABLE—4 ANTICONVULSANT ACTIVITY OF 2-ARYLIMINO-3-(2'-PYRIDYL)-4-THIAZOLIDINONE(II)

Sl. No.	Protection %	Mortality % after 24 hrs
1	20	60
2	40	40
3	20	60
4	60	40
5	20	80
6	20	40
7	40	40
8	80	20
9	20	20
10	20	40

Compounds were administered intraperitoneally at a dose of 100 mg/kg

Determination of Fungicidal activity¹⁰ in in vitro. Six species of fungi were used in the present study *Apergillus terreus*, *Aspergillus nidulans*, *Candida albicans*, *Cladosporium herbarum*, *Fusarium moniliforme*, *Mucor mucedo* Saboralld's broth (peptone 10.0 gm/liter, dextrose 20.0 gm/litre, pH 6.0 approx) was used as the test medium, compounds were dissolved in alcohol, 1.0 ml of test solution (100 µg/ml) was added to each tube containing equal amount of media. Tubes were autoclaved at 15 lbs for 15 minutes prior to inoculation with suitable species of fungus, after inoculation tubes were incubated at 26±2° for 7 days and the vegetative growth recorded visually in each case (Table 5 and 6)

Result and Discussion

The synthesized 2-arylimino-3-(2'-pyridyl)-4-thiazolidinones were tested for amoebicidal activity at 1 : 1000 dilution. Sl.No. 3, 4 and 6 showed amoebicidal activity (Table 1) and from 2-arylimino 3(2'-substituted pyridyl 3')-4-thiazolidanones Sl. No.2,4 and 6 were found to be good amoebicidal (Table 2).

TABLE—5 ANTIFUNGAL SCREENING OF 2-ARYLIMINO-3-(2'-PYRIDYL)-4-THIAZOLIDINONE (II)

Sl. No.	<i>Cladosporium herbarum</i>	<i>Candida albicans</i>	<i>Aspergillus terreus</i>	<i>Aspergillus nidulans</i>	<i>Fusarium moniliforme</i>	<i>Mucor mucedo</i>
Control	++++	++++	++++	++++	++++	++++
1	++	+	++	-	+	±
2	++	+±	-	++	+	+
3	-	-	±	+	±	+
4	-	-	-	+	+	±
5	++++	++++	++++±	+++	-	+++
6	+	-	±	±	+++	-
7	+++	++	++	+++	++	++
8	±	±	±	+±	+	+
9	-	±	±	+	-	+
10	++++	++++	++++	++	+++	+++

++ to ++++ = good growth, positive utilization and no fungicidal activity.
 ± to +± = Slight growth, slight fungicidal activity.
 - = No growth, fungicidal activity.

TABLE—6 ANTIFUNGAL SCREENING OF 2-ARYLIMINO-3-(2'-SUBSTITUTED PYRIDYL 3')-4-THIAZOLIDINONE (IV)

Sl. No.	<i>Cladosporium herbarum</i>	<i>Candida albicans</i>	<i>Aspergillus terreus</i>	<i>Aspergillus nidulans</i>	<i>Fusarium moniliforme</i>	<i>Mucor mucedo</i>
Control	++++	++++	++++	++++	++++	++++
1	++	++	x±	+±	+±	+++
2	-	-	+	+±	+±	+±
3	++	++	+	++	+	-
4	++++	++++	+±	+++	+++	+++
5	++	+±	++	+	++	++
6	++	+±	-	++	++	+
7	+	-	+	+	+±	+±
8	+++	+++	+++	+++	+++	+++
9	+	-	-	+±	-	+
10	++	++	++	++	+++	++

++ to ++++ = good growth, positive utilization and no fungicidal activity.

± to +± = slight growth, slight fungicidal activity.

- = no growth, fungicidal activity.

Four compounds from 2-aryl imino-3-(2'-pyridyl)-4-thiazolidinones were tested for cysticidal activity of which 2-*p*-tolylimino 3(2'-pyridyl)-4-thiazolidinone was most active (Table 3).

The synthesized 2-aryl imino 3(2'-pyridyl)-4-thiazolidinones were tested for fungicidal activity. Sl.No. 3,4,6 and 9 were good fungicidal (Table 5) and from 2-Aryl imino 3(2'-substituted pyridyl 3')-4-thiazolidinone Sl. No. 2,7 and 9 were found good fungicidal (Table 6).

Anticonvulsant activity of the 2-aryl imino 3(2'-pyridyl)-4-thiazolidinones were done (Table 4) Sl.No. 8 shows maximum protection and minimum mortality and Sl. No. 5 shows minimum protection and maximum mortality. It appears that *o*- and *m*-substituents are less effective than *p*-substituent.

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References

1. A. R. SURREY, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 71, 3354.
2. H. D. TROUTMAN and L. M. LONG, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 70, 346.
3. W. J. DORAN and H. A. SHOVLÉ, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1938, 3, 193.
4. K. JIROKINUGAWA and N. HINOSHI, *Yakugakuzasshi*, 1966, 86, 95.
5. B. S. KAUSHIVA and N. ANAND, *J. Sci. Ind. Res. India* 1956, 15C, 460.
6. A. C. ROY and P. C. GUHA, *J. Sci. Ind. Res. India*, 1950, 9B, 262.
7. P. GRAMMATICAKIS, *Bull. Soc. Chim. France*, 1959, 480.
8. B. N. SINGH, U. SAXENA and S. S. IYER, *Indian J. Expt. Biol.*, 1965, 3, 110.
9. S. S. PARMAR, C. D. DWIVEDI, A. CHAUDHARI and T. K. GUPTA, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1972, 15, 99.
10. T. N. SRIVASTAVA, S. N. BHATTACHARYA, J. DASGUPTA and S. K. TANDON, *Indian J. Microbiology*, 1968, 8, 65.